

STUDYING OF THE DIALECT PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS CHARACTERIZING THE RELATION OF THE CARRIER OF TRADITIONAL CULTURE

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the issue of studying of the dialect phraseological units characterizing the relation of the carrier of traditional culture by the way, to language, the speech at Russian classes in school. The author claims that studying at school of lexicon and phraseology of dialects in terms of their conceptual importance in national culture promotes understanding of the language as a mechanism accumulating cultural experience of the people by pupils, and the choice as a material of the dialect phraseological units with the language component reflecting national tradition of speech norms and values promotes formation of skill to carry out reflection – linguistic and ethical – over somebody’s and own word.

Key words: phraseological units, traditional culture, Russian classes in school, pupils, speech norms and values promotes formation of skill.

The topic of the interrelated study of language and national culture, which is topical in modern linguo-methodology, implies not only the search for new methodologically productive forms for the implementation of tasks related to this topic, but also the involvement of new linguistic material as a didactic basis of the Russian language lesson. The dialect language, representing the world picture of a carrier of traditional culture, allows to organize the educational study of axiologically significant concepts, categories, thought stereotypes. One of such concepts of Russian linguoculture, including the traditional one, is the concept of Language. The attitude to language - in its instrumental function, spiritual,

aesthetic - is reflected in precedent expressions - dialect phraseological expressions that characterise and evaluate human speech activity. According to N. F. Alefirenko, precedents have 'high axiological character' and 'are carriers of socially sanctioned evaluations' [1, p. 115]. [1, c. 115].

Thus, the study of folk colloquialisms from the point of view of their 'axiological' and conceptual significance in the national culture contributes to the students' understanding of language as a mechanism that accumulates the cultural experience of the people, and the choice of dialect phraseological expressions with the component "language", reflecting the cultural tradition of speech norms and values, as the research material implies the formation of one of the most difficult communicative skills - the skill of reflection (linguistic and ethical) on others' and own words. In addition, the cognitive significance of both the material and the research itself lies in obtaining knowledge that prevents intercultural barriers and helps to understand the values of another culture and national character.

This article presents the materials of the tested research 'Secrets of good speech', the didactic basis of which was formed by phraseological expressions of Yaroslavl colloquialisms, which create images of the language-speech of a carrier of traditional culture. Expressive and figurative stable expressions will help students to create both a speech portrait of the speaker being evaluated and a portrait of the 'speech normaliser', which will help to form an idea of the communicative norm and its violations from the point of view of a person who is not sophisticated in matters of speech culture.

The content and logic of the study are provided by the methods and techniques demanded in the study of programme topics in Russian language: observation of language material, identification of grammatically productive model of phraseological combinations, lexical, semantic (component) and etymological analysis, allowing to reconstruct the internal form of the word, which is a source of cultural information. The research consists of two stages: the first one is the study of the value-sense content of phraseological phrases with the component

‘language’ and the formulation of the requirements of good speech postulated in various modern textbooks on rhetoric, speech communication and business communication as communicative imperatives that ensure effective communication. The second stage involves the organisation of special observations of the language material, which allow explaining the ethical and aesthetic aspects of the native speaker's perception of the dialect world picture of language-speech.

When starting to study dialect phraseological expressions representing images of language and speech, pupils learn about one peculiarity of the Russian character, about which N. Lossky wrote in his work ‘The Character of the Russian Man’: ‘Russians and all Slavs have a highly developed value attitude not only to people, but also to all subjects in general’ [7, p. 7]. [7, p. 7], and this ‘value attitude’ is the result of collective experience of comprehension of a concrete reality. Language, speech, word receive axiological comprehension, as well as the house, land, bread, labour, material artefacts and realities of the natural world - all that constituted the value and meaning space of everyday life and the spiritual sphere of man.

First of all, let us draw the students' attention to the productive grammatical model of “speech” phraseological phrases - “verb + noun in the creative case”:

баландить ‘to talk, talk for nothing’ [19, note 1, p. 31]; бить языком ‘to talk idle talk, talk nonsense’ [19, note 1, p. 50]; блекотать языком ‘to talk a lot, talk, talk idle talk, talk nonsense’ [19, note 1, p. 62]; боронить языком ‘to talk, talk idle talk’ [19, note 2, p. 16]; дрягать языком ‘to talk’ [19, note 4, p. 22]; лебезить языком ‘to talk nonsense’ [19, note 5, p. 123]; колотить языком ‘to talk nonsense’ [20, vol. 1, p. 317]; (ровно щеколда) молотить языком ‘about a woman with a vigorous tongue’ [19, excerpt 8, p. 134]; стричь языком ‘to speak quickly and verbosely’ [19, excerpt 9, p. 79]. The problematic question is What can explain the ‘communicative activity’ of this model, will lead students to the conclusion that the speaker realised the instrumental function of language and its active nature.

Intonation is a reality of national culture: it reflects the national character, which is why observations on the means of creating an acoustic image of Russian

speech are productive from the point of view of obtaining cultural information about the ethnos and its norms and values.

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